

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Assessing horizontal and vertical policy and regulatory governance (in)coherence

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Summary

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report analyzes the policy (in)coherences in the regulatory design between the European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR), as a case of a unilateral transnational environmental trade regulation, and three national public policies (i.e., the national public forest laws of Brazil, Cameroon and Gabon) and three hybrid public-private governance mechanisms (i.e., Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium, Cameroon FLEGT-VPA and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) from key non-EU producer countries (i.e., Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon). The regulatory design of these selected regulations represents a variety of existing domestic mechanisms that, albeit having similar goals, may be impacted by the EUDR's implementation. They were evaluated based on the conceptual nature of interaction (i.e., coordination, cooptation, competition, chaos) of their policy goals, regulatory standards and enforcement mechanisms.

Results show that the EUDR was found to be coherent and coordinated with all selected policies and governance mechanisms in terms of their overarching policy goals (e.g., forest protection) and some implementation and enforcement mechanisms (e.g., similar tools and strategies). However, incoherence is evident in the form of cooptation and competition in some specific goals, regulatory standards and certain implementation and enforcement mechanisms. The report thus underscores that EUDR standards can impact producing countries in more subtle ways than the most commonly anticipated (e.g., sovereignty, costs, market leakage). Governance strategies already underway in some countries (e.g., public policies and private arrangements), including those promoted by other EU regulations (i.e., FLEGT-VPA), can be impacted and delegitimized by the EUDR through cooptation and/or competition among requirements. This finding is a key consideration when assessing the EUDR's future effectiveness in its overarching goal of reducing global deforestation and forest degradation. Despite analyzing (in)coherences by regulatory design, de-facto (in)coherences will depend on the EUDR's implementation and enforcement, such as behavioral reactions by target actors on the demand (i.e., EU) and supply (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) side. The report provides crucial insights for the design of transnational socio-environmental policies. Policy coherence and alignment between the EU and national producer country policies are needed to avoid creating regulatory fragmentation, differing standards, implementation and enforcement uncertainties, and delegitimization of current standards and processes.

2. INTRODUCTION

Land use governance, affecting deforestation and biodiversity conservation, is regulated through a mix of public policies and private governance mechanisms (Begemann et al., 2021; Lambin et al., 2014; Lambin & Thorlakson, 2018; Sotirov et al., 2020). The 1990s saw increased attention to global, transnational, and national environmental biodiversity-related policies. In parallel, non-state actors have increasingly occupied a large space in the environmental governance arena, creating new private governance arrangements (e.g., certification schemes, private-public partnerships, and sectoral agreements) (Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Since commodities have been identified as crucial tropical deforestation drivers (Hosonuma et al., 2012; Pendrill et al., 2022), public and private governance mechanisms regulating the legality and/or sustainability of transnational commodity supply chains (e.g., timber, soy, cattle, palm oil) have likewise increased.

Studies on transnational commodity supply chains have shed light on regional power dynamics, as producers and end consumers are spread across the globe. What once was largely defined as a global South-North producer-consumer relationship of commodities consumption has changed since the 2000s with an increased South-South trade in the new geography of agricultural trade (Schleifer, 2023). This phenomenon is also marked by the challenge encountered by environmental transnational schemes and standards as they try to best "hit the ground" with national regulation and domestic governance (Marques & Eberlein, 2021; van der Ven et al., 2021). Transnational private and public governance arrangements do not act in isolation but highly engage with one another, yet not always coherently. A knowledge gap persists concerning these interplays and how regulatory forms co-evolve, hybridize, compete and reshape other initiatives (Eberlein et al., 2014; Cashore et al., 2021). In particular, understanding the (in)coherences of how environmental biodiversity-related public policies and private governance mechanisms interact is key to identifying leverage points for improved environmental and biodiversity conservation.

As the European Union (EU) adopted its new EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) in 2023 to regulate the legality and sustainability of forest and agricultural commodity supply chains (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024), its effectiveness "on the ground" remains a question. Investigating its relationship and coherence with national public policies and private governance mechanisms of producer countries outside of the EU can inform possible implementation effectiveness. Policy coherence can be referred to as when

public policies and private governance mechanisms can achieve their goals without any significant trade-offs, having their policy instruments and practices aligned to support their goals (Jordan and Lenschow, 2010; Sotirov, 2022).

To address empirical and theoretical knowledge gaps concerning the (in-)coherences of transnational public and private policies (Eberlein et al., 2014), we assess, as a case study, the designed interactions of the EUDR with non-EU producer country policies and governance mechanisms. We answer the following research questions: How do selected producer country policies and governance mechanisms interact with the EUDR regarding their designed goals, instruments, and processes? How does this interaction likely inform designed policy effectiveness?

3. OBJECTIVES

The objective of this report is to assess the policy (in)coherences in the regulatory design between the EUDR and selected national public policies and private governance mechanisms (i.e., national public forest laws, Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium, Cameroon FLEGT-VPA, and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) from selected non-EU key FRC producer countries (Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon). The policy (in)coherence is assessed by their interaction regarding their policy goals, regulatory standards, and implementation and enforcement mechanisms. This assessment can inform opportunities and challenges for better implementing the EUDR, shedding also light on broader questions regarding the regulatory design of transnational environmental policies.

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This report applies an expanded version of Eberlein et al.'s (2014) Transnational Business Governance Interaction Framework (TBGIF) to analyze the interactions and (in)coherences in the design between public policies and private governance mechanisms in the EU (demand side) and Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon (supply side).

Incoherence is defined as when goals, instruments and practices from different governance mechanisms work against each other, in major contradiction. These (in-)coherences can be assessed vertically, within and across scales/levels of governance (e.g., national and international), and horizontally, within and across sectors (e.g., forestry, agriculture, environment). Policy (in)coherence can also be analyzed through the different stages of the regulation cycle, from agenda setting to implementation and monitoring (Eberlein et al., 2014; OECD, 2023).

Eberlein et al.'s (2014) TBGIF defines transnational business governance interactions as “the myriad ways in which governance actors and institutions engage with and react to one another” (p.2). The framework disaggregates the regulatory governance process and proposes analytical questions relevant to each stage. We expand it by applying it not only to transnational business regulation but also to national public policy and regulation (Marques & Eberlein, 2021).

Dimension of interaction	Component of regulatory governance					
	Goal/ Agenda setting	Rules formation	Implementation	Monitoring, information gathering	Compliance promotion, enforcement	Evaluation, review
Who or what interacts						
Drivers and shapers						
Mechanisms and pathways						
Character of interaction						
Effects of interaction						
Change over time						

Figure 1: Eberlein et al.'s (2014) Transnational Business Governance Interactions Framework

The TBGIF provides a framework to analyze each stage of the regulatory process against different dimensions of interaction. The goal/agenda setting stage is when the issue (e.g., deforestation must be regulated) is placed on the regulatory agenda. Following that is rules formation, which is when regulatory standards are negotiated and decided upon. The following stages of implementation, monitoring, compliance, and evaluation assess how the agreed standards and rules in the policy and governance mechanism are implemented (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Eberlein et al., 2014).

The TBGI Framework includes three main levels of actor-centered analysis, described as micro-level (addressing interactions among individuals and organizations in creating and governing a specific governance mechanism); meso-level (addressing interactions among governance mechanisms); and macro-level (addressing interactions among regulatory regimes, which comprises a myriad of governance mechanisms).

In this report, we empirically apply the TBGIF by conducting a meso-level analysis of the interplay and coherence of the EUDR's **regulatory design** with national supply-side public policies and private governance mechanisms at the 'rules formation' phase. We analyze the designed coherence by identifying key drivers and shapers, mechanisms and pathways, and the character of interaction (Figure 2).

Dimension of interactions	Analysis of the 'rules formation' phase (regulatory design) of policies/governance mechanisms			
Selected mechanisms				
Drivers and shapers (policy goal)				
Mechanisms and pathways (instruments, processes)				
Character of interaction (competition, coordination, cooptation, chaos)				

Figure 2: Applied analytical framework to analyze the regulatory design (in)coherences between the EUDR with policies and governance mechanisms from key non-EU producer countries (Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon), based on Eberlein et al.'s TBGIF (2014)

Building on Eberlein et al. (2014), we identify the "drivers and shapers" dimension as the selected policies' and governance mechanisms' problem definitions (e.g., biodiversity loss), policy goals (e.g., tackling global deforestation) and socio-environmental standards (e.g., deforestation-free requirement). The

"mechanisms and pathways" dimension refers to their implementation and enforcement mechanisms. Examples include information and knowledge mechanisms, specific tools, instruments, and monitoring processes (Eberlein et al., 2014). They operate based on different intervention logics, including through rules (e.g., penalties), markets (e.g., market incentives and disincentives), norms and discourses (e.g., naming and shaming), information and resources (e.g., capacity building) (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012).

Finally, the "character of interaction" dimension refers to the types of interaction the governance mechanisms have, based on the previously analyzed aspects. The four different types are: *competition* (e.g., for market, reputation, legitimacy, authority), *coordination* (e.g., from emulation to deliberate collaboration or conscious division of labor, learning from one another), *cooptation* (e.g., from convergence on norms and activities to meta-regulation, hegemony, or dominance), and *chaos* (e.g., unpredictable, undirected interactions, displaying no clear pattern, and where one scheme claiming authority can produce confusion and substantial impacts on the other's process) (Eberlein et al., 2014).

5. METHODS

This report's analysis was based on an in-depth content analysis of the legislative and policy documents assessed. In addition, and to triangulate findings, we referred to existing literature on the selected policies and governance mechanisms. To answer our research questions, we first identified the key policies and governance mechanisms we wanted to analyze in interaction with the EUDR based on the country case study selection (Brazil, Cameroon and Gabon) and selected regulated commodities under the EUDR (i.e., soy and timber). The four mechanisms selected portray different policies and governance mechanisms that may be impacted by or influence the implementation of the EUDR. The selection of these existing national mechanisms is justified based on three criteria: 1) having a coordinated/coherence overarching goal with the EUDR, regarding forest protection; 2) being domestically relevant (national public forest laws) and unique (private-public governance) in their regulatory design; and 3) having a high possibility of impact by the EUDR's implementation due to overlapping standards.

The first mechanism is the national public forest law in each country, namely the Brazil Forest Code, Cameroon Forestry Law and Gabon Forest Code. The other three mechanisms each represent a specific private-public (the Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium and the Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) or public-public (the FLEGT-VPA in Cameroon) environmental governance initiatives already existent in each country. We examined the selected governance mechanisms through a vertical and horizontal coherence lens. Vertically, since the interaction analysis takes different geographical levels into consideration (EU and national), and horizontally since the mechanisms selected regard forest and agricultural products. Furthermore, our analysis takes a 'meso-level approach' by analyzing the interaction between policies and governance mechanisms. This report focuses on the rules formation phase, yet examines the role of actors in the policy agenda-setting, development, adoption and implementation stages.

Secondly, we analyzed the coherence between these policies and governance mechanisms and the EUDR, using the different dimensions selected from the TBGI Framework (Eberlein et al., 2014) (Figure 2). The "who or what interacts" interaction dimension is informed in this report by the policies and governance mechanisms selected to be analyzed in interaction with the EUDR. In applying the analytical dimensions of interactions, we decided to focus on selected TBGI analytical categories. These include "problem definition" and "policy goals and standards" as "drivers and shapers" and "implementation and enforcement

mechanisms" for the "mechanisms and pathways". The "character of interaction" is then presented for each dimension. Our application of each character of interaction takes on our following simplified definitions, based on Eberlein et al. (2014):

- **Coordination:** governance mechanisms are aligned and do not harm each other (e.g., same policy goal of protecting forests and same standard requirements)
- **Competition:** governance mechanisms are aligned in their aim but are in competition, either for money, membership, client adherence, etc. This is the case when a person or organization has to decide between one or the other, or when one governance mechanism/policy can delegitimize and threaten the existence of another (e.g., FSC versus PEFC, FLEGT licenses versus FSC private certification).
- **Cooptation:** governance mechanisms are aligned, but one dominates and/or superimposes key elements of the other (e.g., EU's deforestation-free policy that prohibits products from deforestation regardless if legal or illegal versus national Forest Code that legally allows deforestation under certain conditions)
- **Chaos:** governance mechanisms have no comparison point, and/or their main logic is totally different and contradictory (e.g., the policy goal of forest preservation versus agricultural land expansion)

Additionally, to assess gender considerations in each policy and governance mechanism, we have evaluated whether they include a gender dimension in their regulatory design.

6. RESULTS

The following sections provide empirical data about the interactions between the regulatory design of the EUDR with selected public policies and private governance mechanisms regarding their goals, instruments, and processes, highlighting their (in)coherence. Table 1 provides an overview of the analyzed governance mechanisms and dimensions of interactions.

Table 1: The character of interaction between the regulatory design of the EUDR and key supply-side public policies and private governance mechanisms

Dimension of interactions	The character of interaction of the regulatory design of the selected public policies and private governance mechanisms			
Selected public policies and private governance mechanisms	EUDR & National public forest laws (Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon)	EUDR & Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium	EUDR & Cameroon FLEGT-VPA	EUDR & Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification
Overarching goal	Coordination	Coordination	Coordination	Coordination
Specific goal	Competition	Coordination	Competition	Coordination
Regulatory standards	Cooptation & competition	Cooptation & competition	Cooptation & competition	Coordination & cooptation
Implementation and enforcement mechanisms	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation

6.1 EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products

Policy goals and standards

Learning from the experience of implementing the 2003 Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Action Plan through market creating Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs) and the market correcting EU Timber Regulation (EUTR) (Zeitlin and Overdevest, 2021) coupled with growing scientific evidence about the EU's global consumption impact through imported deforestation (Pendrell et al., 2019), the EU identified the need for a policy change to regulate legal and illegal deforestation and forest degradation driven by forest and agricultural commodity production, trade, and consumption (Berning and Sotirov, 2023; 2024). The EU adopted the EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115, EUDR) to close regulatory gaps in the hitherto existing policy and legal framework that did not directly address deforestation and excluded agricultural commodities (Recitals 32, 38). The EUDR entered into force on 29 June 2023 and will enter into application from 30 December 2024, with an additional six months provided for compliance by micro or small operators (Art. 38). The new regulation will repeal the EUTR with effect from 30 December 2024¹ (Berning & Sotirov, 2024; Köthke et al., 2023).

The EUDR's comparatively ambitious design and quick adoption after a long agenda-setting period was largely driven by environmentally-oriented public actors from EU institutions (e.g., European Commission, European Parliament, Council of the EU), supported by pro-regulatory non-state actors. This particularly included a coalition of European and transnational environmental NGOs such as ClientEarth, FERN, Greenpeace, and WWF. They mobilized EU public actors' and public support for an ambitious EUDR through lobbying, social media and awareness raising campaigns, and their involvement in the European Commission's multi-stakeholder platform. Additionally, several large business actors, such as multinational consumer goods companies and retailers, including Nestlé, Mondelēz International and IKEA, supported the EUDR publicly for their interests in legal certainty, economic benefits from leveled playing fields for legal and sustainable FERC supply chains and managing reputational concerns. Fearing increased administrative burdens and costs, many other business actors (e.g. domestic producers, upstream companies, FERC import-dependent

¹ However, the EUTR continues to apply until 31 December 2027 to timber and timber products produced before 29 June 2023 and placed on the Union market from 30 December 2024.

companies, forest sector companies) shared the EUDR's **overarching goal** of addressing global deforestation but opposed the EUDR as a whole, or specific regulatory changes (e.g., forest degradation definition, geolocation requirements) (Berning and Sotirov, 2024).

The EUDR's main **policy goal** is to prevent the placement and making available on (or export from) the Union market of commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation (Art. 1). The EU thereby seeks to reduce global deforestation, EU-driven greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity loss to achieve the European Green Deal's 2050 climate neutrality and biodiversity loss reduction goals (Art. 1, Recital 13). The EU also seeks to promote Union-wide and global sustainable production and consumption patterns (Recital 18; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024).

To achieve these goals, the EUDR institutionalized a new forest-risk commodity (FRC) sustainability standard to regulate legal and illegal deforestation. The EUDR goes beyond the timber legality rules of the 2003 FLEGT Action Plan, 2005 FLEGT Regulation (Council Regulation (EC) No 2173/2005) and 2010 EU Timber Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 995/2010) – as requested by the EU but defined by producer countries – requiring compliance with a new **deforestation-free standard** (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024). Deforestation-free means that relevant commodities were produced on land that has not been subject to deforestation and that wood has been harvested from the forest without inducing forest degradation, after the retroactive cut-off date of 31 December 2020. Deforestation is defined as “the conversion of forest to agricultural use, whether human-induced or not.” Forest degradation is defined as “structural changes to forest cover, taking the form of the conversion of: (a) primary forests or naturally regenerating forests into plantation forests or into other wooded lands; or (b) primary forests into planted forests” (Art. 2). The review clause provides the possibility to extend the regulatory scope to include other natural ecosystems (Art. 34) to go beyond the EUDR's FAO-based forest definition of “land spanning more than 0,5 hectares with trees higher than 5 meters and a canopy cover of more than 10 %, or trees able to reach those thresholds in situ, excluding land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use (Art. 2)”.

Additionally, the EUDR institutionalized a more comprehensive **legality standard** than the EUTR. The EUTR prohibits the placing of illegally harvested timber (i.e. harvested in contravention of the applicable legislation in the country of harvest) or timber products derived from such timber on the Union market for the first time (Art. 2, 4). The EUDR prohibits the import, but also the intra-EU trade and export, of FRCs and derived products if they have been produced in contravention of

the relevant legislation of the country of production (Art. 3). This includes applicable laws concerning the legal status of the area of FRC production in terms of land use rights, environmental protection and forest-related rules, third parties' rights, labor rights, tax, anti-corruption, trade and customs regulations, human rights protected under international law, and the principle of free, prior and informed consent (Art. 2). The EUDR thereby institutionalized more comprehensive human rights standards; whereas the EUTR was more specific concerning applicable harvesting-related legislation.

Furthermore, the EUDR institutionalized a new **due diligence statement submission obligation** requesting operators to confirm that they conducted due diligence in accordance with the EUDR and that no or only a negligible non-compliance risk with the EUDR's deforestation-free standard or legality standard was found (Art. 3, Annex II).

Implementation and enforcement mechanisms

The EUDR relies on several implementation and enforcement mechanisms to implement its policy goals and regulatory standards. First, the EUDR establishes an EUTR-like but expanded prohibition clause and more detailed due diligence obligations. The EUDR prohibits the import, export, and intra-EU trade of the seven FRCs cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, rubber, soya and wood, and a selection of products that contain, have been fed with or have been made using these commodities (e.g. chocolate, leather, furniture, printed paper) unless three requirements are fulfilled. They must be 1) deforestation-free, 2) they must have been produced in accordance with the relevant legislation of the country of production, and 3) they must be covered by a due diligence statement (Art. 2, 3, Annex I).

The EUDR also obliges importers, exporters, and large traders (i.e. large enterprises that make products available on the EU market) to exercise risk-based due diligence to assess and mitigate risks along their supply chains (Art. 8). The EUDR further develops the EUTR-based three-tiered due diligence system by requesting more detailed specifications for information collection and more comprehensive criteria to consider during the risk assessment and mitigation processes (Berning & Sotirov, 2024; Köthke et al., 2023). This includes the new geolocation requirements of plots of land information to be described by latitude and longitude coordinates and risk assessments in relation to Indigenous people (e.g., the existence of duly reasoned land use or ownership claims). The EUDR also ensures that enterprises along the EU supply chain are responsible for

compliance. At the same time, the EUDR introduced new due diligence simplifications for SME operators (e.g., the possibility to refer to existing due diligence statements) (Art. 8 - 13).

Compared to the EUTR, the EUDR relies on a stronger state-based regulatory approach. FLEGT-licensed wood is no longer granted a green lane to the EU market as it only fulfills the EUDR's timber legality requirement but not the new deforestation-free standard. Similarly, the green lane for timber covered by the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) permits has also been removed. The acceptance of FLEGT licenses as proof of timber legality but not sustainability (i.e. deforestation-free) seeks to respect bilateral commitments, preserve progress achieved with partner countries that reached the FLEGT licensing stage (i.e. Indonesia), and support current VPA partners in reaching this stage. The EUDR also restricted the use of third-party verified schemes (e.g. forest certification) as a compliance-supporting tool. They are now only permitted as an auxiliary tool to support the EUDR's risk assessment obligations if they fulfill the EUDR's information requirements (Recital 81; Art. 10; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024).

Second, the EUDR introduced several innovations to address EUTR-related implementation and enforcement shortcomings in EU Members, such as resource constraints and the overall inconsistent implementation and enforcement across Member States (McDermott & Sotirov, 2018; Köthke & Sotirov, 2024; Köthke et al. 2023). One innovation is the request for a mandatory submission of due diligence statements electronically through a new centralized information system, visible to competent authorities and customs (Art. 28). The new tool is expected to be essential in supporting the 1) identification of operators and trades, 2) detection of higher-risk economic activities, and 3) planning inspections. The EUDR also introduced new risk-based minimum inspection obligations and a new enforcement cost reclaim mechanism for competent authorities (Art. 20, 26). The EUDR empowers competent authorities to take immediate interim measures (e.g. after receiving substantiated concerns), entitles third parties (e.g., NGOs) to review the processing of substantiated concerns by competent authorities, and introduces a new country benchmarking system (Art. 23, 29, 32). This deforestation and forest degradation risk-rating system – categorizing producer countries and parts thereof as low, standard, or high risk – foresees simplified due diligence requirements for operators and traders sourcing relevant products from areas with a low-risk rating and expanded obligations for EU Member States' competent authorities to conduct more mandatory compliance checks in the case of a standard risk and high-risk rating (Art. 13, 16, 29).

Furthermore, the EUDR establishes that Member States' rules on dissuasive penalties must include fines where the maximum fine must be at least 4% of the operators' or trader's annual turnover in the EU. Penalties must also include the confiscation of products and revenues, a temporary exclusion from public procurement processes and public funding access, temporary prohibitions to import, trade, and export FRCs, and the prohibition to exercise simplified due diligence. The Commission must publish a publicly available list of non-compliance judgements (Art. 25). Lastly, the EUDR obliges the Commission and interested Member States to cooperate with producer countries to address deforestation and forest degradation and support them in meeting the EUDR's FRC production standards, for instance, through Forest Partnerships (Art. 30; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024).

Concerning the inclusion of a gender dimension in its regulatory design, in its Recital 6, the EUDR mentions:

"The acceleration of climate change, biodiversity loss and environmental degradation, paired with tangible examples of their devastating effects on nature, human living conditions and local economies, have led to the recognition of the green transition as the defining objective of our time and a matter of **gender equality** and of intergenerational equity".

Despite a recognition of the issue, there are no specific standards related to gender equality. However, Article 30, concerning cooperation with third countries, it states:

"Partnerships and cooperation shall allow the full participation of all stakeholders, including civil society, indigenous peoples, local communities, **women**, the private sector including microenterprises and other SMEs, and smallholders".

Therefore, the inclusion and participation of women is intended as part of its implementation in cooperation with third countries.

6.2 EUDR and National Public Forest Laws (Brazil Forest Code; Cameroon Forestry Law and Gabon Forest Code)

This section compares national public forest laws in the three case study countries as an example of how the EUDR interacts with national legally binding instruments regulating forest and land conservation and use, by design. The Brazilian Forest Code (Law 12.651/2012) was first established in 1934 and amended several times until its latest amendment in 2012. It regulates the protection of native vegetation, protection areas, the supply of forest raw materials, the origin of forest products, and the prevention of forest fires, in private rural lands. Public forests in Brazil are regulated by Law 11.284/2006. The Cameroon Forestry Law (Law 94/01) was adopted in 1994 and entered into force in 1995. Its implementation is governed by Decree No. 95/531 of August 23, 1995, setting out the application of the forestry regime and other subsequent decrees. The revision of the law has been in process since 2008. The Gabon Forest Code was adopted in 2001. A number of laws, decrees, ordinances, and orders have been passed in various fields to ensure its implementation (e.g., the National Technical Guide for Forest Management, adopted in 2004).

Policy goals and standards

The Brazilian Forest Code was first established at the time of the country's industrialization in the 1930s when the government recognized the need to regulate the economic use of forests, which have been used as raw material supply for industries, such as steel and metallurgy. It was understood that the unregulated economic use of such industries and extraction of raw materials could exhaust the supply. Following its amendments, the Forest Code today contains Brazil's sovereign commitment to protect its forests, yet under sustainable development objectives, stating that forests are assets of common interest to all the country's inhabitants. Hence, the Brazilian Forest Code has an **overarching goal** of protecting Brazilian forests, yet a specific **policy goal** of regulating its standards of economic use and extraction (Santos Filho et al., 2015). For instance, its principles affirm the important role of agriculture and forestry in the country's economic growth by providing global food and bioenergy markets (Art. 1, 2). Similar backgrounds exist in Cameroon and Gabon, where the previous generation of forest laws was considered as insufficiently considering sustainability concerns, leading to the development and adoption of the current Forestry Law in Cameroon and the Forest Code in Gabon (Allogo, 2010; Ekoko, 2000). Therefore, the Brazilian Forest Code, the Forestry Law in Cameroon and the

Forest Code in Gabon all have a similar overarching goal to the EUDR of protecting forests and providing areas of protection (*coordination*). However, when it comes to their specific policy goals, there are dissimilar focuses based on country or regional interests. While the national forest laws still permit and aim to provide space for sustainable and economic use of their national forests and land, the EUDR also focuses on the EU's direct impact on reducing deforestation, land degradation, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, which informs the more precise definition of forests and scope of the regulated commodities and products (*competition*).

Unlike the EUDR, the Brazilian Forest Code's **regulatory standards** cover all land territory in Brazil, providing a different definition of forests, considering all native vegetation (e.g., including all biomes, such as the Cerrado and "campos gerais"). Additionally, these different vegetation coverages have to comply with different socio-environmental standards of preserved areas (e.g., in the Amazon Legal area, 80% of forested areas need to be protected, while 35% of the Cerrado area needs to be protected). Allowing a certain percentage of legal deforestation conflicts with the EUDR's deforestation-free requirement (see section 6.1). The situation is similar in Cameroon, where the forest estate is divided into permanent and non-permanent domains. Deforestation (e.g., for agriculture) in the non-permanent forest domain is allowed. Also, Gabon's Forest Code's regulatory standards have their own definitions (e.g., of forest) that differ from those of the EUDR. The EUDR's legality standard is more aligned with national legal frameworks as it requests compliance with producer countries' laws concerning the legal status of the area of production. However, cooptation exists since, despite coordinated goals, the EUDR's deforestation-free standard superimposes national regulatory standards (*cooptation*). On the other hand, competition also arises given the EUDR's specific and not universal scope (i.e., forest definition and commodities). For example, the EUDR would still allow imports from the seven commodities produced in non-forest areas (but which may be still causing conversion of native vegetation land use, land degradation and biodiversity loss) and be potentially non-compliant to the national Forest Code (i.e., deforesting beyond the percentage allowed), and imports from non-regulated commodities (e.g., corn) from forest areas (defined by the EUDR) potentially produced non-compliant to the national Forest Code (*competition*). Concerning the commodities scope, recent studies inform that the EU currently has a 17.5% deforestation exposure from commodities not regulated by the EUDR, such as cashew nuts and corn, the latter having Brazil as its main exporter (Titley, 2024).

Implementation and enforcement mechanisms

Brazil's Forest Code's implementation relies on information provisions and systems monitored by the state (e.g., CAR (Rural Environmental Registry), SISNAMA (National Environment System), Sustainable Forest Management plans, DOF (Forestry Origin Document)), as well as document analysis and in-loco verification by governmental agencies (e.g., IBAMA (Brazilian Institute of the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources)). Enforcement mechanisms include applying criminal sanctions to the misuse and exploitation of vegetation contrary to the provisions of the law, which are considered illegal (Art. 2). Similarly, the Cameroon Forestry Law (Part VI) and the Gabon Forest Code (Art. 262-284) stipulate the State's prerogative for monitoring and law enforcement, prosecution procedures, offenses, and penalties. In this sense, all the national public forest laws and the EUDR take on a strong state-based command and control regulatory approach in applying penalties for non-compliance. Since one of the EUDR's conditions is production in accordance with the relevant legislation of the producer country, compliance proof with these national laws can help prove compliance with the EUDR's legality requirements on land use rights, environmental protection, and forest-related rules (but not with regards to other legality requirements such as labor and human rights, which could be found in other national legislations). Furthermore, national monitoring systems and forest laws can support showing compliance with the EUDR's deforestation-free standards. However, national legislation is only one requirement to prove compliance, since the EUDR - unlike the EUTR - regulates beyond legality through its deforestation-free definition, over-imposing national legislation. On the other side of the coin, given the EUDR's legality requirement, it can pressure and assist the implementation of national forest laws in the producer countries, especially with regard to the areas in its scope (e.g., Amazon in Brazil). Hence, there is an overlap where each legislation can assist the other in proving compliance, yet there is a limited role given their superimposing standards and different scopes (*coordination & cooptation*).

With regards to gender dimensions, none of the national public forest laws include a mention of women or gender equality.

6.3 EUDR and Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium

Similar to the EUDR's adoption, which was largely driven by pressure from certain European civil society, the ASM's agenda-setting started following pressure from European civil society. NGOs influentially campaigned and advocated for the halt of deforestation driven by soy commodity trade. This particularly includes Greenpeace's naming and shaming campaign in 2006, which connected EU meat consumption with soy production in the Amazon (Greenpeace, 2006) (*coordination*). Hence, in 2006, major soybean traders (e.g., members of the Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries (ABIOVE) and the National Association of Grain Exporters (ANEC)) signed Brazil's Amazon Soy Moratorium (ASM) in 2006 with other non-state actors, mainly NGOs. The public sector joined the ASM in 2008. Companies signatories to the ASM agreed not to sell, purchase, or finance soy from deforested areas in the Amazon biome after July 2008. The ASM was renewed annually and became indefinite in 2016 (Inakake de Souza et al., 2016). The ASM is governed through its multi-stakeholder Soy Working Group, and its enforcement highly depends on a monitoring process that includes satellite data from the National Institute for Space Research's (INPE's) Amazon Deforestation Monitoring Project (PRODES) and the state instrument of the Rural Environmental Registry (CAR) (Agrosatélite, n.d.). NGO signatories have a watchdog role and assist in the monitoring process. The state agreed to collaborate with national data, likewise assisting the monitoring system, and formally supporting the initiative nationally.

Policy goals and standards

Both the EUDR and the ASM identified soy production as a key driver of deforestation and thus decided to regulate it to achieve their **overarching goal** of addressing deforestation (*coordination*). Notably, by design, their deforestation-free **specific policy goals** both go beyond Brazil's public legislative framework under the 2012 Forest Code, which allows for more deforestation in the Brazilian Amazon, as compared to the requirements of the EUDR and ASM (*coordination*). On the aspects where their scopes overlap (i.e., soy as the commodity and Amazon as the biome-included in the EUDR's forest definition), their goals are very much aligned.

Regarding **regulatory standards**, the main difference is that the ASM covers only soy as a commodity and has the geographical scope of the Amazon biome, while the EUDR applies to seven commodities and the whole of Brazil, where its

definition of forests applies. The overlap exists since the EUDR covers the whole territory that the ASM covers, which is 116 municipalities in the Amazon biome that have more than 5,000 hectares of soy production (Agrosatélite, n.d.). However, while the ASM takes as its traceability reference for due diligence the size of an aggregated polygon with soy of 25 hectares or more, the EUDR has as its point of reference the relevant product under the regulation, tracing it back to where it was produced, regardless of the size of the polygon. This highlights different strategies (traceability reference by area or by product) to achieve the same policy goal.

Compliance proof with the ASM's socio-environmental standards could potentially support proving compliance with the EUDR's deforestation-free and legality requirements since it also requires adherence to deforestation-free standards, labor rights (no child or labor force), land use rights (as checked by the CAR and Forest Code), and some environmental protection rules. However, the ASM does not regulate forest degradation, anti-corruption, third parties' rights, or other human rights related to production beyond labor rights. Thus, despite coordinated policy goals, the EUDR superimposes its standards, and since the ASM is not part of national legislation (but a private-hybrid governance mechanism), its proved compliance will not be officially recognized and sufficient to comply with the EUDR (*cooptation*). Furthermore, despite similar goals, these mechanisms differ on an important regulatory standard: the cut-off date. While the EUDR established the cut-off date of December 2020, the ASM has a cut-off date of July 2008, reflecting the ASM's long-standing national legitimacy. Furthermore, the EUDR could threaten the ASM's legitimacy and existence due to regulatory incoherences, such as the differences in the cut-off dates (Oliveira et al., 2024) (*competition*).

Implementation and enforcement mechanisms

Both initiatives share relevant implementation and enforcement mechanisms to achieve their policy goals. Similar to the EUDR's prohibition clause, the ASM creates a market disincentive for producers who do not comply with their deforestation-free requirements. The EUDR prohibits the import of relevant commodities and products that do not fulfill its regulatory standards (see section 6.1), whereas the ASM foresees the creation of lists of producers identified by their monitoring system who will not have their soy bought or financed by the signatory companies. Nonetheless, their intervention logic differs in the sense that while the enforcement of ASM's industry-led private standards primarily relies on voluntarily agreed market access restrictions, the EUDR relies on a stronger state-based

regulatory approach since it is a legally binding transnational public policy enforced through hard penalties (see section 6.1).

Regarding enforcement mechanisms, both require similar strategies to check implementation and ensure accountability. The ASM undergoes annual and rigorous monitoring by the different public and private actors in its Soy Working Group, while EUDR enforcement relies on minimum inspection obligations for EU Member States competent authorities (see section 6.1). In both processes, the use of satellite images, land use documents, and some type of field verification can be used. A relevant difference, however, is that while companies signatory to the ASM determine their own traceability mechanisms to comply and decide how to share information and provide transparency, the EUDR establishes due diligence obligations with detailed risk information, assessment, and mitigation obligations, and mandates the submission of due diligence statements through an information system (see section 6.1).

Similar to the EUDR (see section 6.1), the ASM establishes a civil society co-enforcement mechanism by officially granting them a watchdog role. In both cases, these transparency mechanisms ensure that companies who have received concerns or are found to be non-compliant are known to other companies. Despite these similarities in involving civil society and establishing supply chain accountability through transparency, there is a substantial difference in the geographical scope. Unlike the EUDR, which covers the whole EU market (i.e., import, export, and intra-EU trade), the ASM only covers the Amazon region, a small segment of the Brazilian national soy supply chain (*coordination & cooptation*).

Regarding the gender dimension, there is no mention of women or gender equality in the Amazon Soy Moratorium Agreement.

6.4 EUDR and Cameroon FLEGT-VPA

The FLEGT-VPA between the EU and Cameroon was signed in 2010 and adopted (ratified) in 2011. It is a trade agreement aimed at fighting illegal logging in Cameroon to ensure legal Cameroon-EU timber value chains. The VPA was voluntarily negotiated between the two parties, but it became legally binding upon its ratification (Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021). In this way, it is a part of the EU and Cameroon legal frameworks, and its design was co-determined by both parties to the agreement. However, it is mostly aimed at influencing the Cameroonian timber sector. A FLEGT-VPA is meant to lead to a FLEGT licensing

scheme, whereby timber products exported to the EU would be accompanied by a FLEGT license, allowing them a green lane entry to the EU market under the EUTR. However, the EU-Cameroon VPA process has not reached this stage, and the green lane market advantage has been removed under the EUDR (see section 6.1).

Policy goals and standards

The VPA process between the EU and Cameroon was born from a background of weak forest governance and illegal logging issues in Cameroon, as well as Cameroon wanting to secure EU market access under the EUTR (Carodenuto et al., 2024; Wodschow et al., 2016). These developments were related to the rise of illegal logging as a key forest governance problem on the international agenda in the early 2000s (Gulbrandsen & Humphreys, 2006). Thus, the VPA captures one issue (illegality) of the overarching EUDR problem framing related to legal and illegal deforestation and forest degradation driven by FRC production, trade, and consumption (see section 6.1). The VPA's **specific policy goal** is to provide a legal framework for ensuring that timber and timber products exported from Cameroon to the EU are legally produced or acquired (Art. 2). More broadly, its **overarching goal** is to strengthen forest governance, promote Cameroonian timber products, and improve the country's competitiveness in the international marketplace. Overall, both instruments are aligned in their overarching goals of reducing deforestation and land degradation in Cameroon (*coordination*). Yet, their specific goals differ since the Cameroon FLEGT-VPA has a focus on securing Cameroon's timber into the EU market, while the EUDR has a focus on reducing EU-driven deforestation, land degradation and GHG emissions with higher standards that do not ensure Cameroon's timber to be imported into the EU (*competition*).

At its core, the VPA institutionalizes a **legality standard** meant to distinguish lawful from unlawful timber (VPA Annex II). It defines in a set of legality matrices for timber the legality requirements from different titles and supply sources. The legality matrices are based on five criteria, namely administrative and legal aspects, logging and forest management, transport, social aspects, and environmental aspects. The legality standard and the scope of the legislation that it covers are largely convergent with that of the EUDR's legality standard, although the EUDR expands on it by also regulating illegal deforestation through its deforestation-free standard (see section 6.1). At the same time, an element of competition exists between the standards, as the EUDR (offering a more trade-restricting approach) does not recognize VPA's (offering a more trade-

facilitating approach) FLEGT licenses to the full extent anymore, thus undermining to a degree the VPA standard's legitimacy to exist (*cooptation & competition*).

Implementation and enforcement mechanisms

The VPA mandates the establishment of a Legality Verification System (LVS) (Art. 9 and Annex III). Based on the legality standard, the LVS is meant to verify the legality and upstream traceability of timber in circulation in Cameroon. Regarding traceability, the LVS does not specify geolocation requirements, unlike the EUDR (see section 6.1). A key element of the LVS is the FLEGT licensing scheme leading to the issuance of FLEGT licenses to timber products verified as legal (Art. 4 and 7), granting them direct entry to the EU market under the EUTR and FLEGT Regulation. However, a FLEGT license can only prove compliance with the legality requirement under the EUDR (see section 6.1).

To support its implementation, the VPA contains specific provisions on transparency and information publishing (Article 21 and Annex VII) and the participation of stakeholders in implementing the agreement (Article 16 and Annexes III-A, III-B, and X). Similar transparency and information mechanisms exist in the EUDR, including reporting requirements for enterprises, EU Member State authorities, and the European Commission (see section 6.1). Additionally, the VPA includes social, economic and environmental safeguards for local and indigenous communities, aimed at assessing the impact of the VPA on their way of life and taking reasonable and appropriate steps to mitigate any adverse effects (Art. 17), which is similar to a part of the EUDR due diligence requirements (see section 6.1). The VPA also provides for market-related incentives (e.g., promotional campaigns) for access to the EU market (Art. 18), and it includes an independent audit to check the performance and efficiency of the FLEGT licensing scheme (Art. 11). The EUDR reduced this market incentive by removing the green lane for FLEGT licensed timber and timber products while seeking to support relevant VPA partners in reaching the FLEGT licensing stage (Recital 81, Art. 10). In sum, the implementation and enforcement mechanisms of the VPA and the EUDR are mainly aligned with each other (e.g., transparency requirements), although the EUDR superimposes some aspects over the VPA (e.g., removal of green lane market advantage) (*coordination & cooptation*).

Regarding the gender dimension, there is no mention of women or gender equality in the Cameroon FLEGT-VPA.

6.5 EUDR and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification

In 2018, Gabon announced that all Gabonese forest concessions would need to become FSC certified by 2022 (later postponed until 2025), or otherwise cease their operations. This announcement was made in the form of a Presidential Declaration during the former president's visit to Mevang sawmill of Rougier Gabon. Although not clearly specified, the policy is understood to allude to FSC's Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) standard (Pirard et al., 2023). The declaration is non-legally binding, yet it has carried a quasi-legal influence and is further in the process of becoming incorporated into the Gabonese legal framework (M. Cramm, personal communication, July 13, 2023).

Policy goals and standards

The policy stems from economic concerns, namely lacking competitiveness of Gabonese wood products on the international market and related, untapped market potential. Linked to this, the Gabonese timber sector is also perceived to underperform in its contribution to the local economy. In contrast, the EUDR originates more from environmental sustainability-related concerns, as evidenced in its approach to restricting trade in illegally and unsustainably produced FRCs (see section 6.1). The **policy sets the goal** of achieving 100% FSC certification of all forestry operations in Gabon by 2022 (later postponed until 2025). This is meant, as an **overarching goal**, to improve the sustainability and attractiveness of the Gabonese timber sector, help meet the demands of the international markets, and reinforce the country's own policy of sustainable development. Thus, the overarching policy goals of both governance mechanisms are related to sustainability concerns (*coordination*). Regarding their specific goals, despite having a country/regional interest, both overlap in their goal of aiming to improve the sustainability of their supply chains (in Gabon, specifically timber) in a way that does not contradict the other (*coordination*).

Gabon's mandatory FSC policy institutionalizes an **SFM standard**, as set and defined by FSC. Highlighting environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and economically viable forest management, the standard is built around 10 principles covering compliance with laws, workers' rights and employment conditions, Indigenous peoples' rights, community relations, benefits from the forest, environmental values and impacts, management planning, monitoring and assessment, high conservation values, and implementation of management activities (FSC, 2023). Similar to the EUDR's deforestation-free requirement, the SFM standard contains a prohibition on converting natural forests to plantations

or to non-forest land use, with the same cut-off date of 31 December 2020 (see section 6.1). However, unlike the EUDR, the FSC has not developed quantitative thresholds for defining “forest” in terms of area, density, height, etc. (see section 6.1). Both the SFM standard and the EUDR contain a legality requirement, although while the EUDR describes the topical scope of applicable laws, the SFM standard does not do so, rather referring to statutory law and case law, subsidiary regulations, associated administrative procedures, and the national constitution (see section 6.1). Concerning human rights, the SFM standard covers the principle of free, prior and informed consent with reference to indigenous peoples and local communities, as well as the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples. The EUDR covers similar aspects (see section 6.1). The standards are generally coherent with each other (*coordination*), yet the EUDR subsumes and regulates third-party verified standards (like the FSC) by establishing new minimum requirements such as the geolocation requirement (*cooptation*).

Implementation and enforcement mechanisms

Gabon's mandatory FSC certification offers scant detail of mechanisms for ensuring achieving its policy goal. The declaration contains a short note on the government to provide support to the forestry businesses towards FSC certification. Accordingly, spurred by the policy, an agreement between the Gabonese government and FSC in 2020 has launched activities to support businesses in Gabon in acquiring FSC certification and to enhance the marketing of Gabonese wood products on the international market (Pirard et al., 2023). Despite Article 30 (see section 6.1), the EUDR does not contain direct provisions to support businesses in compliance. If a forestry business has not achieved FSC certification by the deadline set, the Gabonese government will withdraw its operating license, thus exercising its law enforcement power, much like EU Member States' having the mandate to sanction businesses in cases of non-compliance with the EUDR (see section 6.1). In addition, with regard to businesses obtaining the FSC certificate and upholding the SFM standard, the FSC system itself relies on independent audits conducted by third-party, accredited organizations, which is meant to ensure the integrity of the system. Overall, the implementation and enforcement mechanisms are thus largely in line and not at odds with each other. Yet, the EUDR's implementation and enforcement mechanisms “dominate”, as it defines the role of external third-party verified schemes, like the FSC, under it (*coordination & cooptation*).

Regarding the gender dimension, there is no direct mention of women or gender equality in the Presidential Declaration. However, the FSC seriously includes gender equality in their standards. FSC defines gender equality as “women and men having equal conditions for realizing their full human rights and for contributing to and benefiting from, economic, social, cultural and political development” (FSC, n.d.). Certain required standards include: equality in employment practices, training opportunities, awarding of contracts, processes of engagement, management activities, and ensuring that men and women are paid the same wage when they do the same work. In addition:

“FSC standard development groups must investigate whether gender equality is secured through national legislation - both in terms of actual legislation and implementation. Where there are gaps between FSC requirements and national legislation, the FSC standard must include indicators beyond national law. Typically these indicators will ensure (additional) training, alternative payment and assignments methods, flexible working hours, parental leave, childcare, etc” (FSC, n.d.).

Therefore, national mandatory FSC certification would include gender equality standards in its implementation.

7. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

How do selected producer country policies and governance mechanisms interact with the EUDR regarding their designed goals, instruments, and processes? How does this interaction likely inform designed policy effectiveness?

This report aims to empirically answer these questions by showing how selected policies and governance mechanisms (i.e., national public forest laws, Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium, Cameroon FLEGT-VPA, and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) interact with the EUDR regarding their policy goals, regulatory standards, and implementation and enforcement mechanisms. Similar patterns appear concerning their 'characters of interaction', yet attention needs to be paid to highlighted incoherences.

Table 2: The detailed character of interaction between the regulatory design of the EUDR and key supply-side public policies and private governance mechanisms, regarding their overarching goal, specific goal, regulatory standards, and implementation and enforcement mechanisms

Analyzed mechanism	EUDR	National public forest law	ASM	Cameroon FLEGT-VPA	Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification
Identified interaction	Overarching goal	Coordination	Coordination	Coordination	Coordination
Supporting text	Address global deforestation	Protect national native vegetation	Address deforestation caused by soy production in the Brazilian Amazon	Fight illegal logging	Increase Gabon's forestry sector sustainability and market attractiveness
Identified interaction	Specific goal	Competition	Coordination	Competition	Coordination
Supporting text	Reduce EU's contribution to deforestation, GHGs emissions and biodiversity loss by preventing import of commodities and products associated with deforestation on the EU market	Regulate economic use and extraction of national forests	Produce zero-deforestation soy in the Brazilian Amazon biome	Ensure timber and timber products exported from Cameroon to the EU are legally produced or acquired	Achieve 100% FSC certification of all forestry operations in Gabon by 2025
Identified interaction	Regulatory standards	Cooptation & Competition	Cooptation & Competition	Cooptation & Competition	Coordination & cooptation
Supporting text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deforestation-free standard (deforestation and forest degradation definition) - Legality requirement - Due diligence statement submission obligation - Cut-off date 31 December 2020 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standards to regulate national native vegetation (all biomes) - Standards to prevent forest fires - Allows certain percentage of legal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signatory companies do not sell, purchase, or finance soy from properties in the Amazon that were either deforested or are in the Federal list of "slave-like working conditions" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legality standard: matrices for legal timber with five criteria (e.g., logging and forest management) - Offers a trade-facilitating 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SFM Standard (environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and economically viable) - Prohibits conversion of natural forests to plantations or to non-forest land use - Legality requirement

Analyzed mechanism	EUDR	National public forest law	ASM	Cameroon FLEGT-VPA	Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification
		deforestation in each biome	- Regulates 116 municipalities and lands of 5,000 ha or more - Cut-off date July 2008	approach with the EU market	- Human rights principles - Cut-off date 31 December 2020
Identified interaction	Implementation & enforcement mechanisms	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation	Coordination & cooptation
Supporting text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prohibition clause - Importers, exporters, and large traders to exercise risk-based due diligence - Three-tiered due diligence system requesting more detailed information (e.g., geolocation) - FLEGT licenses accepted to prove timber legality, not sustainability (i.e. deforestation-free) - Centralized information system - Third parties (e.g., NGOs) can review the processing of substantiated concerns - Country benchmarking system - Penalties (e.g., fine, confiscation of products, temporary exclusion from funding access) - Member States are to cooperate with producer countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Legally-binding for all private land owners - State information provision and monitoring systems - Document analysis - In-loco verification by state agencies - Criminal sanctions and penalties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-legally binding as it is a private voluntary agreement, but a hybrid mechanism since the government is part of its governance - Market disincentive for producers who do not comply with deforestation-free requirements - Companies need to hire external auditors - The GTS governing the agreement includes the state and NGOs to monitor compliance - Annual monitoring using national deforestation data, remote sensing and CAR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment of a Legality Verification System - FLEGT licensing grants direct entry to the EU market - Provisions of transparency and information provision, including reporting requirements - Social, economic and environmental safeguards for local and indigenous communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Government to provide support to forestry business towards FSC certification - Withdrawal of license to operate if not certified by deadline - Independent third-party audits (FSC)

Firstly, we identified a character of 'coordination' for all mechanisms' overarching policy goals based on their alignments in seeking forest protection. This shows an overarching coherence in the mechanisms' problem definition and in what they seek to achieve. The findings, however, differ when it comes to the specific goals of the national public forest laws and the Cameroon FLEGT-VPA, since there is a competing interest intrinsic to what they wish to achieve with their governance strategy (i.e., also allowing for economic development and 'legal deforestation' and facilitation to the EU market rather than restriction).

Incoherence also appears in regulatory socio-environmental and legality standards. All mechanisms show an interaction character of 'cooptation' since some of the EUDR standards superimpose existing standards of national mechanisms. Yet, the national forest laws, Brazil's ASM and Cameroon's FLEGT-VPA additionally present a character of 'competition'. National forest laws, despite permitting 'legal deforestation' have a broader legally binding scope, providing for superimposed standards when it comes to other vegetation areas (e.g., Cerrado in Brazil) and commodities (e.g., corn), shedding light on the question of which can more efficiently achieve reduced global deforestation. The ASM's and EUDR's cut-off dates stand in competition and can delegitimize the longstanding success of the ASM. Furthermore, since it is a private and voluntary agreement, companies can more easily decide to dissolve it if they need to comply with other foreign policies that contradict it. Cameroon's FLEGT-VPA, albeit legally binding, stands in competition with the EUDR since the latter explicitly gives a limited and lowered recognition of FLEGT licenses. Thus, the EUDR threatens their legitimacy and competes in regulating the soy and timber sectors. The Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification is the only governance mechanism which, instead of competing, would actually coordinate in many standards, including its cut-off date, despite only being applicable to the timber sector.

Lastly, concerning 'implementation and enforcement mechanisms', all mechanisms present an interaction character of 'coordination and cooptation' with the EUDR. Coherence is shown in the EUDR's designed way of achieving its objective, be it by using similar tools or strategies (e.g., remote sensing, auditing, due diligence statement, penalties). Yet, incoherence is displayed through cooptation characteristics since it also superimposes existing national enforcement mechanisms. The results have also highlighted some specificities for each of the analyzed mechanisms. For example, whether mechanisms are governed publicly (e.g., national forest laws) or privately (e.g., Brazilian Amazon

Soy Moratorium) can impact their ability to prove compliance with EUDR requirements (e.g., legality).

An important finding is that no governance interaction presented a 'chaotic' interaction since, based on our definition of this characterization, all dimensions had points of comparison and a similar overarching policy goal. This may be partly due to the selected mechanisms, which were already selected based on the fact that they will possibly be impacted by or influence the EUDR, but also because this analysis regards only the regulatory design stage of these policies and mechanisms. In the design stage of these mechanisms, they may be coherent, but because of imperfect action or leakage, certain interactions can end up being 'chaotic' during implementation. This is explained by Eberlein et al. (2014) as whenever one scheme claims authority over another and through undirected interactions, produces confusion and substantial impacts on the other's process.

Additionally, our short gender dimension assessment revealed that from the policies analyzed, only the EUDR and FSC standards include mention of women and gender equality as part of their implementation. This does not mean that there are no other national policies or governance mechanisms that may include these types of standards, which would help prove compliance with the EUDR's legality requirements, and/or beyond. This reflection sheds light on a limitation of this study, which relates to the reduced selection of analyzed policies and governance mechanisms. Through these cases, we hope to have provided an example of how the EUDR policy (in)coherence analysis can be carried out with domestic country legislation and governance strategy.

Theoretically, we contribute to the state-of-the-art research on policy and governance (in-)coherence of transnational public and private policies by assessing the coherent and incoherent interactions of the regulatory design of the EUDR with the design of non-EU producer country policies and governance mechanisms. Also, by expanding Eberlein et al.'s (2014) TBGIF to also analyze public policies beyond transnational business regulation, we successfully tested how this framework can be used to analyze further public-private interactions in regulating forest and land use change. By selecting three dimensions of interactions from the original framework (i.e., "drivers and shapers", "mechanisms and pathways", and "character of interaction") and by focusing on one phase of the regulatory governance cycle ("rules formation" – regulatory design), the analysis was focused and provided coherent points of comparison between the policies and governance mechanisms analyzed.

Our research further adds to the current literature by showing that in its design, the EUDR may be coherent with policy goals and certain implementation and enforcement mechanisms of producer country policies and governance mechanisms, but its incoherent 'cooptation' and 'competitive' characteristics with regard to standards and certain enforcement mechanisms may cause conflict with national policies and governance mechanisms. Conflict can stem from, for example, incoherent cut-off dates, deforestation definition, commodity scope, and EUDR non-recognition or limited recognition of existing standards such as FLEGT licenses and certification (standards).

This should be a point of attention when observing its implementation effects and effectiveness in non-EU producer countries. EUDR standards can impact producing countries in more subtle ways than the most commonly anticipated (e.g., sovereignty, costs, market leakage). Governance strategies already underway in some countries (e.g., public policies and private arrangements), including those promoted by other EU regulations (i.e., FLEGT-VPA), can be impacted and delegitimized by the EUDR through cooptation and/or competition among requirements. This finding is a key consideration when assessing the EUDR's future effectiveness in its overarching goal of reducing global deforestation and forest degradation.

Finally, the report provides crucial insights for the design of transnational socio-environmental policies. Policy coherence and alignment between the EU and national producer country policies are needed to avoid creating regulatory fragmentation, differing standards, implementation and enforcement uncertainties, and delegitimization of current standards and processes, which could lower implementation effectiveness. Incoherence can also increase effective costs and governance challenges for producing countries and regulatory authorities. Despite informing likely designed policy effectiveness, based on our (in)coherence analysis, we did not conduct a systematic review on effectiveness, which we recommend as potential future research to be conducted, especially once the EUDR has been fully implemented.

8. PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

In this report, we analyzed policy (in)coherences in the regulatory design between the European Union Regulation on Deforestation-free products (EUDR) and four national public policies and private governance mechanisms (i.e., national public forest laws, Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium, Cameroon FLEGT-VPA and Gabon Mandatory FSC Certification) from key non-EU producer countries (i.e., Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon). They were evaluated based on the conceptual nature of interaction (i.e., coordination, cooptation, competition, chaos) of their policy goals, regulatory standards and enforcement mechanisms.

We identified patterns in their character of interaction, mainly being coherent in their overarching policy goals and to a certain degree in their enforcement mechanisms, but revealing cooptation and competitive characteristics with regards to specific goals, regulatory standards and some enforcement mechanisms. The report underscores that EUDR standards can impact producing countries in more subtle ways than the most commonly anticipated (e.g., sovereignty, costs, market leakage). Governance strategies already underway in some countries (e.g., public policies and private arrangements), including those promoted by other EU regulations (i.e., FLEGT-VPA) can be impacted and delegitimized by the EUDR through cooptation and/or competition among requirements. This finding is a key consideration when assessing the EUDR's future effectiveness in its overarching goal of reducing global deforestation and forest degradation. The report provides crucial insights for the design of transnational socio-environmental policies. Policy coherence and alignment between the EU and national producer country policies are needed to avoid creating regulatory fragmentation, differing standards, implementation and enforcement uncertainties, and delegitimization of current standards and processes.

These results will be complemented by the Work Package 5 reports, which will analyze the implementation of the EUDR and behavioral change in greater detail. This will complement the results presented here regarding the regulatory design interaction and coherence of the EUDR with producer country policies and governance mechanisms.

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